

Tabebuin and tecomaquinone-III-dimeric quinones from *Tabebuia rosea*

Poonam Khandelwal and Pahup Singh*

Centre of Advanced Studies, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : pahupsingh@yahoo.co.uk

Manuscript received 1 August 2007, revised 30 November 2007, accepted 30 November 2007

Abstract : Two dimeric C₃₀ quinones-tabebuin and tecomaquinone-III have been isolated from the heartwood of *Tabebuia rosea* in addition to the previously reported 1,4-naphthoquinone derivatives. Both the dimeric quinones are reported for the first time from this plant.

Keywords : Tabebuin, tecomaquinone-III, *Tabebuia rosea*, Bignoniaceae.

Introduction

Continuing our study on coloured pigments from the heartwoods of various Bignoniaceae¹, we re-examined the heartwood of *Tabebuia rosea* DC. (Bignoniaceae). It is an ornamental tree with multiannular masses of light pink flowers and belongs to typical tropical and sub tropical areas. It is a native of Brazil. Its roots is prescribed as drink in scorpion-sting and its wood-tar has been used in various skin diseases². Previous work on this plant included the isolation of several C₁₅ naphthoquinone congeners related to lapachol, and a dimeric C₃₀ quinone, tecomaquinone-I from the heartwood³, bark⁴ and roots⁵. β -Lapachone one of its constituents displayed a potent inhibitor of transcriptase activity from myeloblastosis virus and *Rauscher* murine leukemia virus. In addition, it affects eukaryotic DNA-dependent DNA-polymerase activity⁶. Several naphthoquinones including diosquinone and trimeric naphthoquinone derivative conocurvone have shown cytotoxic and anti-HIV activities⁷⁻⁹. An antimicrobial naphthoquinone pigment, cribrarione, was isolated from *Cribraria purpurea*¹⁰.

In this paper, we now report the isolation and characterization of tabebuin (1) and tecomaquinone-III (2) as dimeric quinones from the heartwood of *Tabebuia rosea*. Both of these pigments are reported second time from the nature and first time from *T. rosea*. Earlier tabebuin (1) was reported from *T. avellanadae*¹¹ and tecomaquinone-III (2) was isolated from *T. pentaphylla*¹². Numbering in compounds (1) and (2) is arbitrary and is done for indicating ¹³C chemical shift of various carbon atoms.

Results and discussion

Tabebuin (1) was obtained as pale orange needles, m.p. 211–212° and has molecular formula C₃₁H₂₆O₅, [M]⁺ 478. It contains one methoxy (3.92 ppm), one aromatic methyl (1.68 ppm) and two *gem*-dimethyl groups (1.82 and 1.84 ppm). Methylene protons of pyran ring appear as a pair of double doublets (2.35 and 2.43 ppm) which couple with a methine proton (dd) under oxygen function (4.88 ppm). Aromatic protons exhibit signals in the region 6.46 to 8.22 ppm. The ¹³C NMR spectrum displayed 31 carbon signals, among which four are methyls, one is methylene, twelve are methine and fourteen are quaternary carbon atoms. Nature of various carbon atoms was ascertained by DEPT 135 experiment. Tabebuin shows a strong quinone

carbonyl absorption at 1662 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum which is substantiated by the presence of carbonyl carbon atoms at 180.76 and 175.4 ppm in its ^{13}C NMR spectrum. It gives electronic absorptions at 250, 270, 323 and 384 nm similar to that of dihydrolapachenole in the UV spectrum. Its mass spectrum besides molecular ion shows two characteristic major fragments at m/z 240 and 238 corresponding to lapachenole and a hydroxymethylanthraquinone moieties. The former ion loses a methyl radical to form an ion at m/z 225, while latter ion extrudes three molecules of CO successively to form ions at m/z 210, 182 and 154.

Tecomaquinone-III (2), was isolated as dark violet crystals, m.p. $219\text{--}222^\circ$, high resolution mass spectrometry has established $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_5$; $[\text{M}]^+$ 466.1785 as its molecular formula. It is reversibly reduced with sodium dithionite indicating its quinonoid nature. It exhibits a strong quinone carbonyl absorption at 1672 cm^{-1} which is further supported by the presence of singlets at 185.70 and 178.12 ppm in its ^{13}C NMR spectrum. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum exhibited the presence of 30 carbons, among which four are methyls, one is methylene, eleven are methine and fourteen are quaternary carbons. Nature of various carbon atoms was established by DEPT 135 experiments. An electronic absorption at 484 nm in UV-Vis spectrum confirms the presence of quinonoid chromophore in the molecule. The ^1H NMR spectrum comprises of two methyl singlets (1.50 and 1.53 ppm), coupled vinyl doublets (5.80 and 6.71 ppm, J 10 Hz each), two further methyl singlets (1.08 and 1.39 ppm) and a methine double-doublet at 4.73 ppm coupled to a methylene multiplet at 1.88 ppm revealing the presence of $-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}(\text{OH})\text{Me}_2$ side chain which is substantiated by the appearance of base peak at m/z 393 resulting by the expulsion of $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}$ side chain from molecular ion.

Experimental

General : Column chromatography (CC) : neutral alumina, deactivated with 10% aq. AcOH. Prep. TLC : Merck silica gel 60F₂₅₄ precoated glass plates, Optical rotation : JAS CO DIP-370 digital polarimeter, UV spectra : Hitachi U-200 spectrophotometer; λ_{max} (ϵ) in nm. IR spectra : FT-IR Nicolet-Magna-550 and Shimadzu 8400s spectrophotometers, ν in cm^{-1} , ^1H and ^{13}C NMR JEOL AL 300 MHz and Bruker Avance DRX 500 FT spectrometers; δ in ppm, J in Hz, MS : JEOL JMS-SX 102A and JEOL D-300 spectrometers; in m/z (rel.%).

Plant material : The plant material was collected from the garden of Bajaj Nagar, Jaipur, Rajasthan and duly identified by Department of Botany, University of

Rajasthan, where a voucher specimen of *Tabebuia rosea* is deposited with herbarium number RU BL 11334.

Extraction and isolation : Air-dried and finely powdered heartwood shavings (3 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$) over water-bath for 12 h \times 3 times. The extract was concentrated to dryness under vacuo, taken in ether and then extracted with 2 *N* Na_2CO_3 solution. The sodium carbonate soluble fraction (acidic fraction) was then treated with 6 *N* HCl to get yellow coloured lapachol (50 g). Sodium carbonate insoluble part (neutral fraction) was washed with distilled H_2O , dried and chromatographed over neutral alumina (deactivated with 10% aq. AcOH) to give seven fractions; fraction-1 (petroleum ether), fraction-2 (petroleum ether-benzene, 4 : 1), fraction-3 (petroleum ether-benzene, 3 : 1), fraction-4 (petroleum ether-benzene, 1 : 1), fraction-5 (petroleum ether-benzene, 1 : 3), fraction-6 (benzene) and fraction-7 (benzene-ethyl acetate, 1 : 1). Fraction-1 could not be worked out being a complex mixture. Fraction-2 afforded deoxylapachol as pale yellow needles (60 mg) and tecomaquinone-I as blue-green crystals (150 mg) after prep. TLC (petroleum ether-benzene, 1 : 1). Fraction-3 yielded 2-isopropenyl-naphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-4,9-dione (58 mg) as yellow needles and tabebuin (80 mg) as pale orange needles after prep. TLC (pet-ether-benzene, 1 : 1). Fraction-4 showed a single spot on TLC plate and yielded dehydroiso- α -lapachone as golden yellow flakes (95 mg). Fraction-5 on prep. TLC (benzene) afforded orange red needles of dehydro- α -lapachone (110 mg). Fraction-6 on prep. TLC (benzene- CH_2Cl_2 , 1 : 1, several developments) gave dark violet crystals (80 mg) of tecomaquinone-III. Fraction-7 was a mixture of stigmasteol and β -sitosterol (180 mg).

Tabebuin : Elution with petroleum-ether- C_6H_6 (3 : 1) gave orange red solution displaying two distinct spots on TLC which was separated by prep. TLC (petroleum ether-benzene, 1 : 1). Band with lower R_f value was worked out as pale orange needles, m.p. $211\text{--}212^\circ$. $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 95^\circ$ (CHCl_3); IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 1662, 1628, 1590, 1375, 1350, 1100, 950, 760, 700 cm^{-1} ; UV (ethanol) λ_{max} : 250, 270, 323, 333, 384 nm; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.68 (3H, s, ArMe), 1.82, 1.84 (6H, s, Me_2C), 2.32 (1H, dd, J 13.7, 8.4 Hz), 2.40 (1H, dd, J 13.7, 6.4 Hz), 4.87 (1H, dbr, J 8.4, 6.4 Hz), 6.46 (1H, s, Ar-H), 6.9 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.5 (3H, m, $3 \times$ Ar-H), 7.75 (2H, m, $2 \times$ Ar-H), 8.22 (4H, m, $4 \times$ Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (75.45 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 18.04 q (C-12 Me), 24.43 q, 25.76 q (Me_2C), 31.96 q (OMe), 38.30 t (C-7), 55.67 d (C-8), 74.50 s (C-6), 103.77 d (C-9), 104.16 d (C-1), 117.21 s (C-10a), 121.30 d (C-4), 121.73 d (C-

20), 125.48 d (C-16), 125.97 (C-2), 126.19 s (C-4a), 126.83 d (C-3), 126.96 d (C-13), 131.41 s (C-14a and C-18a), 132.50 s (C-19a), 133.02 s (C-13a), 133.68 d (C-15), 133.87 d (C-18), 140.61 s (C-8a), 149.44 s (C-4a), 151.74 s (C-10), 166.96 s (C-11), 173.24 s (C-14), 180.73 s (C-19). Chemical shifts of some of the carbons are exchangeable. EIMS : 70 eV, m/z (rel. int.) 478 [M]⁺(10) C₃₁H₂₆O₅, 240 [M-C₁₅H₁₀O₃]⁺ (100), 238 [M-C₁₆H₁₆O₂]⁺ (50), 225 [240-Me]⁺ (87), 210 [238-CO]⁺ (21), 182 [210-CO]⁺ (10), 154 [182-CO]⁺ (3), 153 [154-H]⁺ (10).

Tecomaquinone-III : Elution with C₆H₆ afforded a dark violet solution which was purified by prep. TLC in C₆H₆-CH₂Cl₂ (1 : 1) to give dark violet crystals, m.p. 219–222°. UV (CHCl₃) λ_{max} : 252, 269, 278, 341, 354sh, 524 nm; λ_{max} (MeOH) : 484 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3530, 3450, 1672, 1655, 1631, 1591, 1344, 1254, 1200 cm⁻¹; HREIMS : 466.1816 [M⁺] (C₃₀H₂₆O₅ requires 466.1780); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.08, 1.39 [6H, s, Me₂C(OH)], 1.50, 1.53 (6H, s, Me₂C), 1.83 (1H, dd, *J* 14.6, 3.4 Hz), 1.91 (1H, dd, *J* 14.6, 9.4 Hz), 2.33 (1H, brs, OH), 4.73 (1H, dd, *J* 9.4, 3.4 Hz, CH-CH₂), 5.80, 6.71 (1H each, d, *J* 10 Hz, CH=CH), 7.48, 7.55 (1H each, dt, *J* 6.9, 1.3 Hz, Ar-H), 7.72 (2H, m, 2 × Ar-H), 8.16 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.39 (1H, d, *J* 3.1 Hz, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DEPT 135, CDCl₃) : δ 25.83 d (C-9), 27.27 q (C-4'Me), 27.52 q (C-3'Me), 29.42 q (C-6'Me), 30.72 q (C-5'Me), 51.49 t (C-1'), 70.29 s (C-2'), 76.15 s (C-6), 111.78 s (C-8a), 116.59 s (C-8b), 118.0 d (C-7), 121.21 d (C-8), 121.82 d (C-1), 124.18 s (C-4a), 124.46 s (C-16b), 125.24 s (C-9a), 126.01 d (C-2), 126.39 d (C-3), 126.55 d (C-4), 127.08 d (C-12), 130.81 d (C-13), 130.84 s (C-14a), 132.14 s (C-10a), 133.57 d (C-14), 134.11 d (C-11), 139.77 d (C-4b), 146.36 s (C-16a), 152.93 s (C-15a), 178.18 s (C-15), 185.80 s (C-10). Chemical shifts of some of the carbons are exchangeable. EIMS : 70 eV, m/z (rel. int.) 466 [M]⁺ (33) C₃₀H₂₆O₅, 451 [M-Me]⁺ (14), 433 [451-H₂O]⁺ (7), 394 (47), 393 [M-C₄H₉O]⁺ (100), 378 [393-Me]⁺ (12), 364 (15), 255 (7), 189 (7).

Acknowledgement

Authors thank Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan for providing laboratory facilities and RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow for providing mass spectral data. Authors are grateful to Prof. Y. Fujimoto, Chemistry and Materials Science, Tokyo, Institute of Technology, Japan for recording 2D NMR spectra of tecomaquinone-III. Authors are also thankful to the CSIR for Emeritus Scientistship to PS and UGC, New Delhi for financial assistance in the form of major research projects.

References

1. A. R. Jassbi, Pahup Singh, S. Jain and S. Tahara, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **87**, 820.
2. M. Pio Correa, "Dicionario das plantas uteis do Brazil e das exoticas cultivadae", ed. Ministerio da Agricultura Rio de Janeiro, 1952, Vol. IV, p. 318.
3. K. C. Joshi, L. Prakash and Pahup Singh, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 942.
4. K. C. Joshi, Pahup Singh and Girraj Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect B*, 1976, **14**, 637.
5. S. Jain, Parul Chauhan and Pahup Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 946.
6. A. R. Schuerich and W. Wehrli, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1978, **84**, 197.
7. B. A. Adeniyi, M. F. Robert, H. Chai and H. H. S. Fong, *Phytother. Res.*, 2003, **17**, 282.
8. L. A. Decostered, I. C. Parsons, K. R. Gustafson, J. H. Cardellina II, J. B. Mc Mohan, G. M. Cragg, Y. Murata, L. K. Pannell, J. R. Steiner, J. Clardy and M. R. Boyd, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 6673.
9. J. R. Dai, L. A. Decostered, K. R. Gustafson, J. H. Cardellina II, G. N. Gray and M. R. Boyd, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1994, **57**, 1511.
10. A. Naoe, M. Ishibashi and Y. Yamamoto, *Tetrahedron*, 2003, **59**, 3433.
11. A. R. Burnett and R. H. Thomson, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1967, 2100.
12. P. K. Sharma, R. N. Khanna, B. K. Rohatgi and R. H. Thomson, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 632.